

percent. Thus, early seedling submergence has little effect on heading duration and productivity of submergence-tolerant varieties. The submergence of the seedlings would not interfere with or delay heading during RGA of tolerant lines. ■

Kneeing ability test of promising deep water rice selections

R. C. Chaudhary, V. N. Sahai, and S. Saran, Rajendra Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna I, India

Varieties for deepwater rice areas must be able to bend toward the vertical axis so the first three leaves are above the water level. This characteristic known as kneeing ability prevents seed damage by water and aquatic fauna.

Promising deepwater rice cultivars were tested for kneeing ability by a method proposed by Vergara et al (1976). Kneeing was scored on a scale of 1 to 9. Good kneeing ability was shown in 28 of the 58 entries tested (see table). Most entries, which scored 3 and 5, are either local cultivars or pure line selections. Thus, high-volume crossing is needed to create more variability for deepwater rices. ■

Kneeing ability scores of some promising deep-water rice cultures at Patna, India.

Score	Entries (no.)	Entries
3	7	CNL231 B/B, IET6890, KD7-9-20, IET6860, FRG 7, Tilokkachari, and CN603.
5	21	C64-117, BR14, BR46, KLG108-P, KLG173-P, Barobar, KR2-17, KR2-27, CNL108, CM5-13, CN539, CR1009, IET6857, IET6859, NPS7, CN540, CN643, NC486/77, Achra 108/1 and IR7732-RGA-13-A96-1.

Evaluation of rice cultures for submergence tolerance and grain yield under lowland conditions at Tripura

A. K. Ghosh and S. Sardana, ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region, Tripura Centre, P. O. Lambucherra, West Tripura PIN-799210; and A.N. Asthana, senior scientist (plant breeding), ICAR Res. Complex, Shilong, 793004 India

Hills cover two-thirds of Tripura. The remaining one-third is valley. Most of the lowland valley becomes flooded because rainfall averages 2,000 mm/year. Tripura rice fields remain submerged 1-10 days after a rain, depending upon field drainage. The heavy rainfall and poor drainage prevent high yielding, semidwarf varieties from getting established or giving good yields.

To select a suitable rice variety, 60 new cultures and 13 local varieties were screened for submergence tolerance and grain yield during the rainy seasons of

1978 and 1979. The testing submerged 10- and 20-day-old seedlings in a water tank for 7 days. The water depth ranged from 25 to 30 cm above the seedlings.

Seedling survival increased with age. Most of the varieties showed poor recovery after submergence; however, a few – CR149-5010-228, CR149-3295-4-205, CR210-1005, CR210-1009, CR213-1020-374, and IR2071-176-1-2 – were promising (see table). Some of the cultures gave higher yields than Jagannath, Mahasuri and other local varieties under lowland situations (25-50 cm). Culture CR 149-5010-228 gave the highest average yield during the rainy season.

A seedling emergence percentage count taken on the fourth and seventh days revealed some varieties had faster seedling elongation in water, but reduced survival. They included Jalaplaba, Chenab 64-117, CR149-1744, RAU21-68-1-2, FR13A, Madhukar and Chakia 59. These are all tall traditional varieties and are more suitable for deep water conditions (50-100 cm). ■

Submergence tolerance of some rice cultures and their average grain yield under medium lowland condition, 1978, 1979 rainy season, Tripura, India.^a

Variety	Seedling survival (%)		Av grain yield (t/ha)	Seedling emergence (%) of 10-day-old seedlings	
	10 DS	20 DS		4th day	7th day
CR149-5010-228	68(5)	80(3)	4.4	13	23
CR149-3295-4-205	54(6)	98(2)	3.4	8	11
CR149-1744	68(5)	80(3)	1.5	20	28
CR213-1020-374	40(7)	92(2)	3.5	9	15
RAU21-68-1-2	40(7)	96(2)	2.9	17	34
CR213-1021	27(9)	83(3)	3.2	2	2
CR210-1009	34(8)	69(5)	3.9	–	4
CR210-1005	17(9)	78(4)	3.8	–	4
IR2071-176-1-2	44(7)	89(3)	3.4	2	10
Jagannath ^b	6(9)	81(3)	3.1	–	4
RP1064-14-2-2	38(8)	94(2)	2.7	–	4
Mahasuri ^b	42(7)	87(3)	2.7	12	15
Pijum	21(9)	72(4)	2.4	–	8
Majirsail	19(9)	74(4)	1.7	2	4
BR46	29(9)	68(5)	1.3	6	9
BR14	12(9)	70(5)	1.4	–	–
Chenab 64-117	44(7)	85(3)	1.2	23	30
FR13A	25(9)	76(4)	2.6	10	30
Madhukar	33(8)	75(4)	–	15	25
Chakia 59	51(6)	80(3)	–	13	27
Jalaj	36(8)	54(6)	1.4	15	22
Jaladhi 1	24(9)	44(7)	0.7	8	13
Jaladhi 2	11(9)	78(4)	1.4	9	14
Jalaplaba	37(8)	78(4)	1.8	24	33
C.D. (5%)	–	–	.393	–	–
C.V. %	–	–	15	–	–

^aFigures in the parentheses indicate score value of survival (%). DS = date of seeding. ^bCheck variety.